

RESPIRATORY DISEASES IN CHILDREN

¹Ganiyeva.D.K., ²Shaykhova.M.I., ³Karimova.D.I.

^{1,2,3}Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14189537>

Abstract. *Children's health problems are no different from adults. Although they may have comparable illnesses, there may be considerable differences in how severe they are. Because children of different ages will have different problems, it is crucial for caregivers to know what to look out for more. Early childhood is the age group in which children most commonly experience health problems. For this reason, while they are in that age range, it is essential to provide them more attention. Their respiratory system is a prevalent issue. The diagnosis and treatment of the condition may benefit if the caregiver is able to identify the warning signals. This can become crucial in avoiding additional issues that could affect the children's general health, including growth and development that is acceptable for their age, as well as appropriate psychological and behavioral qualities. Because the human respiratory system is exposed to the environment, allowing carbon dioxide to escape and air to enter, it is a prime location for pathogens that may cause disease. In youngsters, who have not yet developed protection to common viruses and bacteria that might cause such issues, diseases affecting the respiratory system—the nose, throat, and lungs—are particularly prevalent. Your child may eventually be affected by one of these seven prevalent childhood respiratory conditions. Be aware of the warning signs and symptoms, and if any persist or seem to worsen over time, consult your physician.*

Keywords: *acute respiratory viral infection (ARVI), The common cold, Asthma, Sinusitis, Bronchitis, Pneumonia.*

Relevance. The broad category of upper and middle respiratory tract diseases known as acute respiratory viral infections (ARVIs) are brought on by pathogenic bacteria, or viruses. About 200 pathogens that can produce common clinical symptoms have been found by scientists. This makes it challenging to precisely identify the viral strain that afflicted the child's disease. Experts both domestically and internationally agree that a youngster should expect three to four ARVI bouts annually. The Americans go so far as to clarify. If the child begins attending kindergarten or school, they permit an increase in the frequency of ARVI episodes up to 12 times annually. The reason for this, according to experts, is a dramatic rise in the baby's "acquaintances" with viruses that it had never encountered before. Therefore, it's crucial to realize that if a 3-year-old child has started to actively communicate with classmates, you don't always need to freak out when he becomes sick for the first time.

The purpose of this study. The lungs, windpipe, voice box, throat, mouth, and nose are all parts of the respiratory system. Through the mouth or nose, air enters the respiratory system. It warms and humidifies the air if it enters the nostrils, also known as the nares. By removing dust and other particles that enter the nose through the air we breathe, tiny hairs known as cilia—pronounced SIL-ee-uh—protect the nasal airways and other respiratory system components. The throat, also known as the pharynx (pronounced FAR-inks), is where the nasal cavity and the mouth, the two airway openings, meet. Since the pharynx transports both food and air, it is a component of both the respiratory and digestive systems.

This tract splits in two at the base of the pharynx: one for food (the esophagus, pronounced ih-SAH-fuh-gus), which goes to the stomach, and another for air. When we swallow, a little flap of tissue called the epiglottis (pronounced eh-pih-GLAH-tus) covers the air-only route, preventing food and fluids from entering the lungs. The upper portion of the air-only pipe is called the larynx, or voice box. A pair of vocal cords in this small tube vibrate to produce sound. The airway that continues beneath the larynx is called the trachea, or windpipe. To keep the trachea open, strong rings of cartilage reinforce its walls (pronounced TRAY-kee-uh).

Additionally, cilia that line the trachea remove fluids and other objects from the airway, preventing them from entering the lungs. The trachea splits into left and right bronchi (pronounced BRAHN-kye) at its bottom end, and these air tubes join the lungs. The bronchi in the lungs divide into smaller bronchi and more tiny tubes known as bronchioles (pronounced BRAHN-kee-olz). The actual exchange of carbon dioxide and oxygen occurs in the tiny air sacs known as alveoli, which are where bronchioles terminate. The lungs of every individual contain hundreds of millions of alveoli. The term "bronchial tree" refers to this arrangement of alveoli, bronchioles, and bronchi.

Additionally, the lungs' elastic tissues enable them to expand and contract without losing their form. A thin lining known as the pleura (pronounced PLUR-uh) covers them. The airtight box that contains the heart, lungs, bronchial tree, and other organs is called the thorax, or chest cavity (pronounced THOR-aks). The diaphragm (pronounced DYE-uh-fram) is a big muscle that forms the bottom of the thorax, while the ribs and other muscles construct the top and sides. The lungs and other contents of the chest cavity are surrounded by a protective cage made of the chest walls. To survive, our body's cells require oxygen. As our cells function, carbon dioxide is produced in our body.

The respiratory system, which includes the lungs, allows the body to absorb oxygen from the air and expel carbon dioxide from the air. The diaphragm descends into the abdomen during inhalation, while the rib muscles pull the ribs higher and outward. This expands the chest cavity and draws air into the lungs through the mouth or nose.

The diaphragm rises and the muscles of the chest wall relax during exhalation, which reduces the size of the chest cavity and forces air out of the respiratory system through the mouth or nose. Each inhalation causes a significant amount of air to fill the millions of alveoli every few seconds. The capillaries, which are tiny blood vessels that line the alveolar walls, allow oxygen to diffuse from the alveoli to the blood. Red blood cells' hemoglobin absorbs oxygen once it enters the circulation. After returning to the heart, this oxygen-rich blood is pumped via the arteries to all of the body's oxygen-hungry tissues.

Oxygen is released from hemoglobin and enters the cells through the minuscule capillaries found in bodily tissues. The carbon dioxide that the cells produce throughout their activities travels from the cells into the capillaries, where the majority of it dissolves in the blood's plasma. The veins then carry the carbon dioxide-rich blood back to the heart. This blood is pushed from the heart to the lungs, where carbon dioxide is expelled through the alveoli.

Materials and methods of research. symptoms of ARVI. One of the most prevalent diseases that both adults and children can contract is ARVI. At some point in their lives, everyone on the planet has come into contact with this illness. -increased body temperature (normal seasonal acute respiratory viral infections are rarely accompanied by a fever of more than 38.5 ° C, but even such an increase in body temperature can be dangerous for infants and newborns); -tearfulness; -cough (in the early stages of the disease it

is dry, but then becomes productive with coughing up sputum); -increased mucus secretion from the nose (sometimes it can acquire a yellowish or even greenish tint); -redness of the sclera; -tearfulness.

Viruses are the cause of ARVI development. Pathogens invade the upper respiratory tract's mucous membrane, where they infiltrate the cells and interfere with their regular functions. A runny nose or cough is caused by the local inflammation and mucus production that accompany this process.

Child hypothermia; excessively dry air (hyperthermia reduces the protective function of the mucous membrane of the upper respiratory tract, increasing the aggressiveness of pathogens); congenital or acquired immunodeficiency; malnutrition or prematurity; abnormalities of the upper respiratory tract; and exacerbation of chronic somatic diseases are factors that increase the risk of infection.

A sick person is the source of the illness. Both contaminated personal hygiene products and airborne droplets can spread viruses.

The common cold. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, the common cold, often known as an upper respiratory infection, is the main reason children miss school due to illness. According to the Children's Hospital of Philadelphia, the average youngster will get six to eight colds year.

Typical symptoms include a runny nose.

-Sore throat.

-Coughing.

-Sneezing.

-Body pains and headaches.

According to Williamson, viruses that cause common colds are "usually less severe than influenza and have a lower risk of causing a secondary pneumonia". Adults and children have relatively similar symptoms, albeit children may also have a little temperature, whereas adults typically do not.

Asthma. According to the CDC, asthma affects around 6.2 million children in the US, or over 8% of all children in the country. Coughing is one of the symptoms of asthma, a potentially fatal lung condition.

-Tightness or pressure in the chest.

- Breathing difficulties or shortness of breath.

-Exhaling with wheezing or whistling.

Adult symptoms are often similar to those of youngsters. Adults, however, could have more enduring symptoms. In addition to asthma, children are more prone than adults to have allergies.

Sinusitis. Sinusitis, often known as a sinus infection, is an enlargement or inflammation of the sinus lining tissue. An infection may result from fluid accumulation in these often air-filled sacs behind the nose and eye. It can be brought on by allergies or frequently coexists with a cold or the flu.

-Face pain and pressure, especially behind the eyes and nose, are symptoms of sinusitis.

-Having a heavy, crowded feeling.

-A runny nose and coughing.

-Post-nasal drip, which can result in nausea or vomiting, poor breath, and sore throat.

Symptoms may last longer in children than in adults. Taking an over-the-counter decongestant or irrigating the sinuses with a net pot may help reduce inflammation and discomfort. Your pediatrician might recommend an antibiotic if there is a bacterial illness. Surgery may be advised to clear the clogged regions in children who have chronic sinusitis.

Bronchitis. Inflammation of the bronchi, the lungs' large breathing tubes, is known as bronchitis. Usually brought on by a virus, it can appear after a cold or the flu. A common symptom that may last for three to four weeks after the virus has left the body is a persistent cough. A runny nose is one of the symptoms that may accompany a chesty cough.

- Congestion and chest pain.
- Chills and fever.
- A general sense of fatigue or malaise.
- Wheezing.
- Sore throat.

Children who have bronchitis may swallow mucus instead of coughing it up, but the symptoms are essentially the same as those of adults. Children who have chronic sinusitis, asthma, or allergies are more likely to get bronchitis. Consult your pediatrician if you are unsure because asthma can occasionally be confused with bronchitis or vice versa. Usually, the goal of treatment is to reduce symptoms.

Pneumonia. An infection of the lungs causes pneumonia, which can develop into a serious illness. Among the symptoms are:

- Rapid breathing.
- Shivers and high temperature.
- Coughing.
- Weary.
- Chest pain, particularly during breathing.

Children may have less noticeable symptoms than adults, making diagnosis more challenging. According to the World Health Organization, 15% of all pediatric deaths are caused by pneumonia.

Pneumonia may develop after your child has had a cold, the flu, or strep throat, and it can be caused by viruses, bacteria, or fungi. Antibiotics can be used to treat bacterial pneumonia. Although there isn't a specific treatment that can treat viral pneumonia, your doctor might recommend an antiviral drug to reduce the illness's length. Your youngster may also feel a little better with rest and lots of fluids. Vaccines against whooping cough, measles, and pneumococcus can lower your child's risk of contracting pneumonia.

Researches and discussion. Every year, millions of Americans suffer from colds, which are typically mild and go away on their own in a few days. Your youngster will recover more quickly if they get enough rest and drink lots of water. However, if your child is younger than two, do not give them over-the-counter cold remedies. The Food and Drug Administration updated its guidelines in 2008, stating that children under the age of two should not use over-the-counter cough and cold products due to the possibility of serious side effects, such as convulsions, elevated heart rates, unconsciousness, and even death.

Numerous things, including exposure to allergens like pet dander or dust or pollen, can cause asthma episodes. Children with asthma may be more susceptible to pneumonia or bronchitis.

According to the American Lung Association, it is also the third most common reason why children under the age of 15 are admitted to hospitals. See a pediatrician if your child appears to be coughing a lot, coughing during physical activity, or experiencing dyspnea. You should also see a doctor for an evaluation if you have recurrent bouts of bronchitis or wheeze or whistle. Preventing respiratory diseases is the most crucial strategy. To lessen the spread of these prevalent diseases, heed these easy tips:

-Cover your sneeze or cough. It's crucial to cover your cough or sneeze, ideally with your elbow or a tissue rather than your bare hand, as these illnesses are usually spread by coughing and sneezing.

-Frequently wash your hands. Saliva and nasal secretions can spread respiratory diseases through coughing in close proximity, direct contact (e.g., shaking hands), or contact with shared surfaces (e.g., doorknobs and worktops). To eliminate any bacteria or viruses that could be remaining on your skin, make sure to wash for at least 20 seconds with warm water and soap.

-Do not touch your lips, nose, or eyes. Numerous viruses frequently enter the body through these locations.

-Reduce interactions with ill people. Avoid interacting with sick people as much as you can. Keeping a sick child home from school is another aspect of this.

-Obtain a flu vaccination. The flu vaccine is the best way to prevent influenza since it drastically lowers your risk of getting pneumonia or needing to be admitted to the hospital if you come into contact with someone who has it.

REFERENCES

1. Ubaidullaev A.M., Ismailov Sh.U., Sharafutdinova G.Kh. Problem sleep apnea syndrome in pulmonology (Guidelines for doctors), Tashkent, 1998.
2. Ubaydullaev A.M., Yakimova M.A., Uzakova G.T. Bronchial asthma. Tashkent, 2001
3. Ubaydullaev A.M., Agzamov R.A., Gaffarov Sh.R. Upka sarcoidosis. T, 2000,
4. Fedoseev G.B., Khlopotova G.P. Bronchial asthma. M., Medicine, 1988
5. Fedoseev G.B., Ubaidullaev A.M. Early diagnosis and primary prevention of bronchial asthma. Tashkent, 1989
6. Fedoseev G.B. Bronchial asthma. M., 1996
7. Khomenko A.G. Tuberculosis yesterday, today and tomorrow. The problem of tuberculosis,